

EXPLORING THE EFFECTS OF CULTURE IN METABOLIC SYNDROME FOR SOUTH ASIAN ADOLESCENTS

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Topic: Metabolic Syndrome

Title: Exploring the Effects of Culture in Metabolic Syndrome for South Asian Adolescents

Objectives: To examine trends in prior metabolic syndrome research among South Asian adolescents aged 14-25 to identify under-researched cultural and dietary factors that impact current literature's accuracy.

Background: Every 1 in 4 South Asians is at risk for developing metabolic syndrome before the age of 30. This cluster of 5 conditions that severely increases the risk of heart disease, stroke and Type 2 diabetes, begins developing silently during adolescence. Yet, adolescent-focused research remains limited. Even more limited is the literature, which fails to include the cultural eating habits rich in carbs and fats that intensify the risk of metabolic syndrome. By analyzing trends, this study identifies critical gaps in how culture and diet are addressed in metabolic health research for South Asians.

Methods: To inspect the literature, we generated 1218 preliminary articles pertaining to metabolic syndrome in South Asian adolescents in Web of Science by inputting the following search terms: *metabolic syndrome*, *South Asia*, and *adolescents*. Subsequently, we excluded articles not relevant to metabolic syndrome by examining the article title, journal names and times cited. Of the 634 articles that remained, we exported the bibliometric data of our top 100 cited sources into Google Sheets for analysis.

Results: After analyzing the 6 most frequently referenced keywords in the articles, 26 articles prioritized culture, diet and/or lifestyle within the context of metabolic syndrome among South Asian adolescents. All 26 articles mentioned either *diet*, *lifestyle*, *factors* and/or *risk* in their title. Additionally, all of them had either *metabolic syndrome*, *adolescents*, *diet* and/or *risk* in their author keywords.

Conclusions: Because factors like culture and diet are underrepresented, researchers should prioritize more culturally open approaches to health literacy not only to explore how tradition and lifestyle intersect with adolescent health but to tailor messages that are relevant and life-saving to the experiences of the youth.

Keyword 1: South Asian adolescents

Keyword 2: South Asian culture

Keyword 3: Nutrition

Keyword 4: Diet

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